

ESTIMATION OF FORMALDEHYDE BY ROMIJN'S METHOD IN PRESENCE OF AMMONIUM SALTS

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In the hypiodite oxidation method of estimating formaldehyde, ammonium salts interfere. A mixture of 3% mercuric chloride and about 40% potassium iodide has been found to prevent completely this interference. The usual black precipitate, produced by the action of hypiodite on ammonium salts, does not appear; the solution remains clear and excellent results are obtained for formaldehyde.

Romijn's method (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1897, **36**, 19) of estimating formaldehyde consists in treating formaldehyde solution with a definite volume of standard iodine solution and an excess of sodium hydroxide solution. The excess of iodine is estimated by acidifying the reaction mixture with hydrochloric acid and titrating the liberated iodine with hypo, using starch as indicator. Although the method is good, it is not applicable to dilute solutions containing formaldehyde and ammonium salts. When the reaction mixture is made alkaline, ammonia reacts with hypiodite, affording a black precipitate of indefinite composition consisting of a mixture of NI_3 and $\text{NI}_3 \cdot \text{NH}_3$ (Ephraim, "Inorganic Chemistry", 1939, p. 738). Even a trace of ammonium salt takes up a large amount of iodine and the interference is profound.

Dilute solutions of formaldehyde and ammonium salts react very slowly at room temperature to form hexamethylenetetramine and the reaction soon attains an equilibrium because of the reverse reaction becoming more prominent with the increase in acidity. The acid is produced by the complete hydrolysis of the tetramine salt on account of its very weak basicity.

If the solution is made alkaline, the rate of formation of tetramine increases; the maximum rate has been observed at p_{H} 8 by Polley, Winkler and Nicholls (*Canadian J. Res.*, 1947, **25B**, 525). In Romijn's method excess of sodium hydroxide is used. In presence of ammonium salts the formaldehyde not only undergoes oxidation but also reacts with the ammonia produced by the excess of alkali. This constitutes the second interference produced by ammonium salts.

It has been found that on addition of a solution of mercuric chloride, containing a large excess of potassium iodide, to the formaldehyde solution, the interferences produced by ammonium salts are completely prevented.

Ammonia probably forms a complex with $\text{K}_2(\text{HgI}_4)$. Nicholls and Willits (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **56**, 769) consider that the composition of the Nessler's precipitate is $\text{NH}_2\text{Hg}_2\text{I}_3$ which is, however soluble in excess of KI. In the present procedure of estimation due to the addition of a large excess of potassium iodide, no precipitate appears, and the complex formed with ammonia remains in solution. Thus, ammonia is prevented from reacting with either hypiodite or formaldehyde.

Bougault and Gros (*J. pharm. chim.*, 1922, **26**, 5) have described a method of estimating formaldehyde by oxidation with alkaline Nessler's solution. After keeping

for 15 minutes or more, a greyish yellow precipitate appears consisting of mercury and mercurous salts, which are quantitatively reoxidised by acidified iodine solution, the excess of iodine being titrated back with hypo. In the present method, where alkaline Nessler's solution containing excess of potassium iodide has been used, the reaction mixture remains clear throughout and no precipitate appears. Hence, the oxidant here is the sodium hypiodite and not the Nessler's solution. Moreover, it has been found that alkaline Nessler's solution, containing excess of potassium iodide, oxidises formaldehyde very slowly, producing a pure grey precipitate of mercury, and in 20 minutes only 25% of the aldehyde is oxidised. In presence of hypoiodite the oxidation is complete in 20 minutes. Sodium hypoiodite appears to be a more powerful oxidising agent, and hence, acts as the oxidant in the method described.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Procedure.—The solution of a mixture of mercuric chloride and potassium iodide was prepared freshly by dissolving 3 g. of mercuric chloride in 100 c.c. of water and adding to it 50 g. of potassium iodide. The solution had a slight yellowish tinge and was used on the same day. Both the chemicals used were pure. The formaldehyde solution (5 c.c.) to be estimated was taken by a pipette in a pyrex conical flask of 100 c.c. capacity. The concentration of formaldehyde was 0.1 *M* and that of ammonium chloride, 0.05*M* or less. About 8 c.c. of HgCl_2 -KI solution was added to the conical flask along with 12.5 c.c. of standard 0.1*N* iodine solution from a burette. The reaction mixture was made alkaline by adding 2 c.c. of 1*N*-NaOH from a graduated pipette. The conical flask was corked and kept for at least 20 minutes at about 20°. It was shaken several times during this period. Finally its contents were acidified with 4 c.c. of 1*N*-HCl and the iodine liberated was titrated with 0.05*N*-hypo solution. A blank was run simultaneously, similar in all respects except for the addition of formaldehyde solution. The difference in the hypo readings gave the formaldehyde present in the mixture (1 c.c. of 0.05*N*-hypo solution = 0.75 mg. of HCHO).

Table I records the results of analysis of mixtures of 0.2*M* formaldehyde and 0.1*M* ammonium chloride in various proportions. In all the mixtures the final concentration of formaldehyde was 0.1 *M*. The actual value for formaldehyde was determined by double diluting the 0.2 *M* solution with water and estimating by Romijn's method. All mixtures were prepared fresh and immediately estimated.

TABLE I

H. CHO actually present = 20 c.c.

Conc. of NH_4Cl present.	HgCl_2 -KI soln. added to 5 c.c. of mixture.	H. CHO found.	Error.
(1) Nil	Nil		...
(2) <i>M</i> /40	5 c.c.	19.95 c.c.	-0.25%
(3) <i>M</i> /30	5	19.95	-0.25
(4) <i>M</i> /20	8	20.0	±0.0
(5) <i>M</i> /15	10	20.05	+0.25
(6) <i>M</i> /10	10	20.09	+0.25

(From 2 to 6 the I_2 added is 30% to 35% in excess of what is required).

Interference due to Large Excess of I₂.—Romijn's method as modified by Singer (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1930, 13, 43) lays down that I₂ added should be at least double the amount actually required. Experiments were carried out with pure solutions of formaldehyde to assess the minimum amount of excess of I₂ required for complete oxidation of formaldehyde in presence of HgCl₂-KI solution. The results as presented in Table II show that about 33% in excess is enough to afford constant and correct values for the aldehyde.

TABLE II

In each experiment 5 c.c. of 0.075 M-HCHO was estimated and the amount of NaOH added was 2 c.c. of 1N solution. H.CHO actually present = 15.0 c.c.

HgCl ₂ -KI solution added.	N/20-I ₂ added.	I ₂ added in excess.	H.CHO found.	%Error.
N/1	30 c.c.	15 c.c. (100%)	15.00 c.c.	±0.0
"	25	10 (66%)	14.95	-0.35
"	20	5 (33%)	14.40	-4.0
"	18	3 (20%)	14.00	-6.5
8 c.c.	18	3 (20%)	14.50	-3.5
8	20	5 (33%)	14.95	-0.35

When a large excess of I₂ was used for estimating mixtures of ammonium chloride and formaldehyde, higher values for the aldehyde were obtained. It was found that 33% - 50% I₂ in excess furnished good results.

TABLE III

[5 c.c. of a mixture of 0.075M.HCHO and 0.05 M-NH₄Cl estimated with 0.1 N iodine solution using 1N NaOH (2-3 c.c.) and 0.05 N-hypo.]

Conc. of NH₄Cl=0.05M. H.CHO actually present=15.0 c.c. HgCl₂-KI soln. added=8 c.c.

0.1 N-I ₂ added.	I ₂ in excess.	H.CHO found.	%Error.
10 c.c.	2.5 c.c. (33%)	15.05 c.c.	+0.33
12	5.5 (73%)	15.10	+0.66
15	7.5 (100%)	15.40	+2.6
20	12.5 (166%)	16.00	+6.6

Mixtures of HCHO, NH₄Cl and (CH₂)₆N₄ Analysed.—Dorer and Ozimic (*Farm. Glasnik*, 1949, 5, No. 9/10, 174) state that Romijn's hypoiodite method of estimating formaldehyde is applicable in presence of hexamethylenetetramine. The present method using HgCl₂-KI solution was also found to be successful in presence of tetramine as elucidated in Table IV. The concentration of formaldehyde in the mixture was 0.075 M.

TABLE IV

Conc. of NH_4Cl soln. = 0.05M.

Conc. of hexamethylene-tetramine.	HgCl_2 -KI soln. added to 5 c.c. of the mixture.	HCHO present.	HCHO found.
0.1 M	8 c.c.	15.0 c.c.	14.95 c.c.
0.2	8	15.0	14.95
0.4	8	15.0	14.95

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